
UNRAVELLING JUDICIAL NARRATIVES: POWER AND SCOPE OF NCLT UNDER SECTION 7 OF IBC, 2016

BY PRAKRITI DABRAL¹

ABSTRACT

Businesses require taking risks and coping with problems on a regular basis, making successful competition crucial for survival. The Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code, 2016 was enacted to provide a unified legislative framework to deal with cases of insolvency and bankruptcy. One of the main features of the Code is that it encourages the Creditor-in-Control regime. It means that the code aims to protect the interests of the creditors. This study focuses on one of the Code's most important provisions. There exists some level of ambiguity with respect to the procedure to even begin the resolution process against the Corporate Debtor by the Financial Creditor. Several perspectives have been given by the Supreme Court of India on the pronouncements given by the Adjudicating Authority for Insolvency and Bankruptcy matters, the National Company Law Tribunal. There lies a series of landmark judgments given by the Supreme Court to lay down the foundation for future cases. However, certain level of confusion and ambiguity still lies. Therefore, this article seeks to address and analyse the rationale behind various judicial pronouncements with respect to Section 7 of the Code which deals with the Initiation of Corporate Insolvency Resolution Process by Financial Creditors.

Keywords: Insolvency, Financial Creditor, Corporate Debtor, Adjudicating Authority, National Company Law Tribunal (NCLT)

I. INTRODUCTION

¹ Author is pursuing BA LLB (Hons.) at CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Pune Lavasa Campus

The economic market and business environment largely depend on capital to run efficiently. Companies and corporations typically obtain this capital from numerous creditors who provide them with the funds needed to run their operations. However, this puts creditors at risk of incurring losses. As a result, the economy as a whole may take severe and unwanted turns.

“Insolvency” refers to a state of financial distress where the person/entity is unable to repay its debts due to insufficiency of funds. This state arises when the entity’s liabilities are more than its assets and hence, puts it in a state of economic distress. However, such a state is not permanent. It means that the company or the entity can recover and become solvent again. Insolvency of a person leads to a “Default” being committed by it which gives way to its creditors to take legal action against it. When such legal action is confirmed by the Court in favor of the Creditor, it becomes “Bankruptcy”. Bankruptcy occurs due to the failure of the resolution mechanism to settle the debts of the Corporate Debtor. This state is permanent and the person cannot return to being solvent.

Insolvency law is significant in providing competent mechanism to deal with situations of insolvency and to ensure that no stakeholder is at a disadvantage. During this process, the rights and remedies available to creditors are suspended and a process of realizing the debtor's assets is carried out in order to equitably distribute the money based on the claims of creditors. The notion of enacting insolvency legislation in India came from the British colonization of India. Before 2016, the subject of Insolvency was dealt by various enactments such as Companies Act, 1956, Companies Act, 2013, Sick Industrial Companies (Special Provisions) Act, 1985, etc. However, they were found to be inadequate. The previous regime favored the debtors where they retained possession and control of their business even during the process of Insolvency. With the implementation of the Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code in 2016, the National Company Law Tribunal, which heard and determined matters for companies and corporations, became the Adjudicating Authority for the corporate insolvency resolution process and liquidation.

As the legislation is a recent one, it has certain unintended consequences which the Government has attempted to resolve by various amendments. However, there is still a long way to go to deal with the confusion with respect to certain provisions of the Code.

II. INSOLVENCY AND BANKRUPTCY CODE, 2016: BACKGROUND

“The Insolvency Code is a legislation which deals with economic matters and, in the larger sense, deals with the economy of the company as a whole.”²

Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code, 2016 was assented to by the President on 25th May, 2016. The Code was a revolutionary measure taken by the Government to improve the country's credit culture. It aims to consolidate all existing insolvency laws and amend all existing legislations relating to restructuring and insolvency of corporate persons, partnership firms and individuals in a time-bound manner so that the assets of such concerned persons could be maximized leading to protection of interests of all stakeholders.³ The Code also provided for the establishment of an Insolvency and Bankruptcy Board of India to regulate and ensure efficient working of the Code.

The legislation was enacted after a long history of Insolvency laws in India. This timeline involved the Sick Industrial Companies (Special Provisions) Act, 1985 whose main aim was the timely detection and expeditious rehabilitation of the sickness of companies. The Act provided for the establishment of the Board for Industrial and Financial Restructuring (BIFR) whose main aim was to restructure and rehabilitate sick industries, unlike the Companies Act, 1956 which provided for winding up of the company itself on becoming sick. As laudable as this legislation was, it proved to be incomplete and being misused. Various committees such as Eradi Committee in 1999, N L Mitra Advisory Group in 2001, J J Irani Committee in 2005 were set up to come up with suggestions and recommendations to form legislation on Insolvency in India. In 2014, Bankruptcy Law Reforms Committee was set up to analyse the legal framework related to insolvency and bankruptcy and submit its report. The recommendations of the committee proved to be of significance in laying the foundation of the Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code, 2016 in the country.

III. SECTION 7 OF INSOLVENCY AND BANKRUPTCY CODE, 2016

Section 7 of the Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code, 2016 outlines the initiation of Corporate Insolvency Resolution Process (CIRP) against the Corporate Debtor by the Financial Creditor. But who is a Financial Creditor? According to Section 5(7) of the Code, a “Financial Creditor” is a person to whom a Financial Debt is owed and it also includes a person to whom such debt

² *Swiss Ribbons Pvt Ltd. V. Union of India (2019) SCC OnLine SC 73 (India)*

³ *The Report of the Bankruptcy Law Reforms Committee Volume 1, 2015,*
https://ibbi.gov.in/BLRCReportVol1_04112015.pdf

is legally transferred or assigned. Section 5(8) of the Code provides the definition of Financial Debt. In other words, a financial creditor is one whose relationship with the entity or enterprise is purely financial contract such as a loan or debt security. Hence, when a Financial Creditor attempts to initiate CIRP against the Corporate Debtor, he takes recourse of Section 7.

The section provides that in the event of a default by the corporate debtor, a Financial Creditor may file an application, either on his own or on behalf of other Financial Creditors, before the Adjudicating Authority. Section 7(4) of the Code states that the Adjudicating Authority has to ascertain the existence of a default within fourteen days of the receipt of the application from the records of the Information Utility or on the basis of any other evidence or proof provided by the Financial Creditor. Section 7(5) proves to be of most significance. It states that if the Adjudicating authority is satisfied that (a) a default has been caused on the debt owed by the Corporate Debtor and (b) the application submitted is complete and (c) there is no disciplinary proceeding pending against the resolution professional proposed in the application made by the Financial Creditor, the Adjudicating Authority may admit the application, thereby initiating CIRP against the Corporate Debtor. However, if the Adjudicating authority is satisfied that (a) a default has not been caused on the debt owed by the Corporate Debtor or (b) the application submitted is incomplete and (c) there are any disciplinary proceedings pending against the resolution professional proposed in the application made by the Financial Creditor, the Adjudicating Authority may reject the application and not initiate CIRP against the Corporate Debtor.

This subsection provided room for uncertainty which led to the conundrum of ascertaining the scope and power of the Adjudicating Authority for an application made by a Financial Creditor. It set out the ambiguity in deciding whether petitions by financial creditors could be admitted or not based on the reasoning of the Adjudicating Authority.

IV. JUDICIAL INTERPRETATIONS OF THE POWERS OF NCLT UNDER SECTION 7 OF IBC: ANALYSIS

The answer to the question as to whether the power conferred to the NCLT under Section 7 of the IBC is discretionary or mandatory in nature has been interpreted by the courts in a series of cases from *ES Krishnamurthy and Ors vs. M/s Bharath Hi-tech Builders Pvt Ltd* (2020) to

Vidarbha Industries Power Ltd vs. Axis Bank Ltd⁴. The series of cases have provided various conflicting and contradicting pronouncements.

In M/s. Innoventive Industries Ltd. Vs. ICICI Bank Ltd⁵, the NCLT had ordered that the Code being a parliamentary statute, would prevail over the Maharashtra Act (referred to the Maharashtra Relief Undertakings (Special Relief Act), 1958) which is a State Statute and hence pronounced that Innoventive Industries Ltd defaulted in payment of the debt. On appeal, NCLAT upheld the order of NCLT. The Apex Court stated that if the financial creditor can prove that a) the was a debt given to the corporate debtor and b) the corporate debtor has defaulted on that debt, then the NCLT “shall” admit the application made by the Financial Creditor under Section 7 of the Code, without considering other matters and merits of the case.

Similarly, in the case of ES Krishnamurthy and Ors vs. M/s Bharath Hi-tech Builders Pvt Ltd⁶, the Supreme Court of India set out the scope of the power of NCLT to admit applications under Section 7 of the Code. In the abovementioned case, the NCLT declined the petition submitted and directed the respondents to settle the debt within 3 months as they believed that initiating CIRP process against the Corporate Debtor would prove to be detrimental to the interests of the Debtor to settle the debts. It further provided that if the creditors are still aggrieved by the settlement, they could approach the Adjudicating Authority. NCLAT, in turn upheld the decision of NCLT. The Apex court held that the NCLT and NCLAT have acted outside their jurisdiction. Under Section 7, the adjudicating authority only has to determine whether the debtor has defaulted on the debt owed or not and based on this determination, it has to either accept or reject the petition filed under Section 7. The Adjudicating authority has no power to compel or direct the parties to settle. They can urge the parties to move to a settlement to meet the aims and objectives of the Code but cannot compel them to come to a settlement by acting as Courts of Equity. In line with this, the Apex Court set aside the orders of NCLT and NCLAT and directed the parties to file a fresh suit before the adjudicating authority.

The Supreme Court took a different interpretation perspective than the abovementioned cases in the case of Vidarbha Industries Power Ltd vs. Axis Bank Ltd.⁷ wherein the Respondent filed for initiation of CIRP against the Appellant under Section 7 of IBC and the appellant filed a Miscellaneous Application to seek to stay on the proceedings under Section 7. However, the

⁴ *Vidarbha Industries Power Ltd vs. Axis Bank Ltd.* (2022) SCC OnLine SC 841

⁵ *Innoventive Industries Limited V. ICICI Bank & Anr.* (2017) SCC OnLine SC 1025

⁶ *ES Krishnamurthy & Ors. V. M/S Bharath Hi Tech Builders Pvt. Ltd.* (2022) 3 SCC 161

⁷ *Supra*, note 04

Adjudicating Authority rejected the application filed by the Appellant stating that the Code aims to dispose of petitions in a time-bound manner and to make active efforts to keep the Corporate Debtor an ongoing concern. NCLAT, in turn, upheld the impugned order of NCLT on the grounds of absence of any legal frailty. The Adjudicating Authority stated that it is mandatory to entertain a petition under Section 7(5)(a) if a debt is present and a default has been caused on that debt. The appellant in the case was unable to pay the unpaid amount because of an ongoing appeal being pending before the Court and hence, they were unable to realise the sum which was payable to the creditors. The appellant contended that due to these being extraordinary circumstances, a petition against them under Section 7 shouldn't be admitted. The respondent contended that Section 7(5)(b) causes a mandatory obligation on the Adjudicating Authority to accept the petition of Financial Creditors on being satisfied that a default has been caused by the Corporate Debtor.

The Supreme Court, setting aside the orders of NCLT and NCLAT, stated that the word "may" has been used in the language of Section 7(5)(a) for a reason. It signifies that the Adjudicating Authority doesn't need to admit the application on the ascertainment of dues and default, rather it is its discretion. This provision is different from Section 9 of the Code wherein, on determination of debt and default by the Corporate Debtor against the Operational Creditor, the Adjudicating Authority "shall" admit the application. Hence, the Adjudicating Authority may take into account the facts, circumstances, and merits of cases before admitting or rejecting petitions. The authority may not admit the petition despite having debt and default if good enough reasons exist to do so. The rationale for this was to ensure that insolvent enterprises may recover themselves to clear the default without being unfairly disadvantaged or penalized by the resolution procedure.

A Review petition was filed against the above judgment of the Apex Court in *Axis Bank Limited vs. Vidarbha Industries Pvt Ltd.*⁸ because the court has overlooked the decision given in the *ES Krishnamurthy case*⁹. The court stated that in the above case, the question was whether the Adjudicating authority could direct the parties to settlement and not whether it was mandatory or discretionary for the Adjudicating authority to admit or reject the application under Section 7 of IBC, 2016. In the same line, the review petition was disposed of.

⁸ *Axis Bank Limited V. Vidarbha Industries Power Limited, 2022 SCC OnLine SC 1339*

⁹ *Supra, note 06*

In *HDFC Bank Ltd. vs John Energy Ltd.*¹⁰, the Adjudicating Authority stated that the Corporate Debtor was not a weak company financially, and although the inadequate liquidity has impacted repayments, the company's financials showed that it is solvent. There was only one financial creditor who was opposed to the idea of restructuring the debts owed by the corporate debtor. Hence, NCLT rejected the application to initiate CIRP against the Corporate Debtor under Section 7 of the Code.

In *M Suresh Kumar Reddy vs. Canara Bank & Ors*¹¹ (May 2023), the financial creditor, Syndicate Bank approved a loan to the corporate debtor, Kranthi Edifice Pvt. Ltd. in the form of a secured overdraft facility with a bank guarantee in favor of the Telangana Government. Later, the corporate debtor requested an extension of the bank guarantee because the Telangana Government was about to encash it. The bank denied the plea, requiring the corporate debtor to repay the entire loan amount. The financial creditor passed an application to initiate CIRP against the Corporate Debtor under Section 7. NCLT admitted the petition and NCLAT dismissed an appeal filed by the director of the corporate debtor. The Supreme Court observed that once NCLT is satisfied that there is a debt and it has become due, there is not much grounds left with it to reject the admission of the application. Thus, the Court affirmed the opinion taken in the cases of *Innoventive Industries*¹² and *E.S Krishnamurthy*, stating that if the corporate debtor's debt is due and payable, the NCLT will accept the financial creditor's claim. The application can only be refused if the debt is not due and payable. The Supreme Court's division bench firmly stated that the *Vidarbha* review case¹³ in no way overruled the *Innoventive Industries* decision, but rather clarified that the judgment was just rendered in the context of the matter at hand.

V. WHAT'S THE WAY AHEAD?

As deliberated before, the Supreme Court has given different interpretations of the power of the National Company Law Tribunal concerning an application filed under Section 7 of the

¹⁰ *HDFC Bank Ltd. vs John Energy Ltd.*, CP(IB) 02(AHM) of 2022, https://nclt.gov.in/gen_pdf.php?filepath=/Efile_Document/ncltdoc/casedoc/2401105034532021/04/Order-Challenge/04_order-Challenge_004_1675143223171409215763d8a83750dc7.pdf

¹¹ *M Suresh Kumar Reddy vs. Canara Bank & Ors.*, Civil Appeal No. 7121 of 2022 https://main.sci.gov.in/supremecourt/2022/31608/31608_2022_14_1502_44326_Judgement_11-May-2023.pdf

¹² *supra*, note 05

¹³ *Supra*, note 08

Code by way of judicial pronouncements. However, the uncertainty surrounding the implementation of the section will persist in future cases.

According to an advisory document¹⁴ dated January 18, 2023, released by the Ministry of Corporate Affairs, it is proposed that if and when the Adjudicating Authority is satisfied that a default has occurred and other requirements specified under the section are fulfilled, it “shall” mandatorily admit the application by the Financial Creditor and initiate CIRP against the Corporate Debtor. It means that if such a proposal is accepted, other merits and factors of the cases would not be considered while admitting or rejecting a petition under Section 7. Moreover, it has also been proposed that the period of 14 days mentioned in the Section should be utilized solely for the determination of the occurrence of default.

However, if such a proposal is accepted, then how will the judicial pronouncement in the Vidarbha Industries case operate? There persists a great deal of confusion. Hence, an amendment of the Code is needed to set the aims and objectives with respect to the concerned section of the code. This will provide the correct strategy for the Adjudicating Authority and the Judiciary to interpret the Section while deciding cases.

VI. CONCLUSION

The confusion of Section 7(5) of the Code being mandatory or discretionary is still there and it causes delay in the admission or rejection of the application by the NCLT and hence, impedes the CIRP process and makes it difficult to keep the company/business a going concern. The Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code of 2016 is a relatively new piece of Indian legislation that is still being improved and corrected. Despite certain limitations, it has proven to be quite important for insolvency resolution in India. Certain improvements need to be made, but in a densely populated country with one of the world's top economies, it takes time to properly design and adopt regulations and legislation that benefit everyone. A robust statute with fewer loopholes will clarify the ambiguity, meeting the Act's original intents and objectives.

¹⁴ <https://www.mca.gov.in/content/dam/mca/pdf/IBC-2016-20230118.pdf>